

ANNUAL PATTERNS OF NUTRIENTS AND CHLOROPHYLL IN A SUBTROPICAL COASTAL LAGOON UNDER THE UPWELLING INFLUENCE (SW OF BAJA-CALIFORNIA PENINSULA)

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Abstract. The coastal lagoon of Bahía-Magdalena, located on the west coast of the Peninsula of Baja-California, is a subtropical ecosystem with an arid climate and very little freshwater input. During the 2005-2011 period the thermohaline properties varied between cold and warm half-yearly periods. They were influenced by the Transitional Water mass transported by the South California Current from February to July and by the Subtropical Surface Water from August to January. The nutrient concentrations increased (viz up to 16 μM of nitrate) from March to June, when the upwelling index was the highest. Similarly, the inter-annual variation of chlorophyll-*a* showed a six-monthly pattern with the highest average monthly concentrations being found in June (5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ *in situ* or 8 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ based on satellite information) and the lowest in December-January. A spatial zoning was also observed in the lagoon with a shallow inner zone that is warmer and richer in chlorophyll-*a* than the deeper closed mouth area. In the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon a spatial-temporal division into two zones and two seasons was repeated year after year with only minor differences. During the first semester in the outer zone, years 2006 and 2007 were colder and nutrient rich while 2010 was warmer, according to the upwelling conditions in the Southern California Region. Hence, among the coastal lagoons that present a prevailing marine influence, the coastal system of Bahía-Magdalena corresponds to an unusual type of subtropical coastal lagoon where the nutrient input is mainly due to upwelling phenomena.

Keywords: inter-annual, intra-annual, biogeochemistry, California Current, choked lagoon, Bahía-Magdalena, Pacific coast, Mexico.

1. - INTRODUCTION

Continental shelf waters represent 8% of the Earth's oceanic surface but it is where nearly 25% of the primary sea production occurs (Walsh, 1989) and where a variety of types of coastal systems, which determine the exchange between land and sea, are found. In these systems, coastal lagoons, making up 13% of the coastal areas worldwide, are predominant (Kjerfve 1994). Coastal lagoons are inland water bodies, usually oriented parallel to the coast, separated from the sea by a barrier and connected to the ocean by one or more restricted inlets (Kjerfve and Magill 1989). In the subtropical climate region bordering, as delimited by Perillo et al. (1999), the Tropics of Cancer and Capricorn (23.5° latitude) and the temperate region (40° latitude), coastal lagoons are subject to a wide climatic diversity ranging from monsoons to desert-like conditions. In all of these climate types the availability of nutrients restricts biological richness (Salomons et al., 2005). Despite this fact, subtropical coastal lagoons have not been studied extensively from a biogeochemical viewpoint, rather it is the ecological aspects that have undergone a more in-depth examination (Kjerfve, 1994).

The wide variety of subtropical coastal lagoons have been classified according to the type of entrance channel into choked, restricted or leaky lagoons (Perillo et al., 1999), distinguished by the freshwater or marine prevailing influence (Abreu et al., 2010) or by the depth and substratum characteristics (Nichols and Boon, 1994). All the same, biological productivity in subtropical coastal lagoons is influenced by hydrodynamic processes such as water residence time (Badylak

1 and Phlips 2004; Phlips et al., 2012), tidal mixing (Abreu et al., 2010) and water column turbidity
2 (Caffrey et al., 2007). In addition to hydrographical factors, the type of littoral vegetation, i.e. salt
3 marsh, mangle, seagrass and seaweed, is also relevant (Phlips et al., 2012; Badylak and Phlips
4 2004) as is the presence of populations of filtering macro-invertebrates, crustaceans and fishes,
5 which may regulate phytoplankton dynamics (Badylak and Phlips 2004; Jiang et al., 2012).

6 A key factor in the primary production of subtropical coastal lagoons is nutrient input where
7 the fluvial contributions may be essential (Coutinho and Mello 2011, Phlips et al., 2012).
8 Upwelling events, rather than continental sources, are the main origin of nutrients transported to
9 the photic layer (Hutchings et al., 1995). So, in the choked, restricted, and leaky lagoons of the
10 arid regions found along the Pacific coast of Mexico (Gilmartin and Relevante, 1978) and
11 southwestern Australia (Hodgkin and Lenanton, 1981), the new nutrients are principally supplied
12 from the sea.

13 In Mexico there are 124 coastal lagoons (Lankford 1977) 60% of which are situated in the
14 subtropical region and 50% on the California Peninsula and its Gulf. The lagoons located on the
15 western shore of Baja-California Peninsula (32-23°N) from the San-Quintín lagoon (40 km²) to the
16 north to the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon (565 km²) to the south are under the sea influence of the
17 California Current. In this coastal zone the climate is dry and arid with northerly winds prevailing
18 throughout the year. However, to the south of southern parallel 28°N south-western and
19 western winds are common in summer and autumn (Zaitsev et al., 2010), which modifies the
20 coastal hydrodynamic (Durazo et al., 2005; Durazo et al., 2011). The largest, deepest and
21 southernmost lagoon of the Baja-California Peninsula, Bahia-Magdalena, is located in this area

22 Due to its wealth of marine resources, the ecological aspects of the aforementioned lagoon
23 were studied extensively, as summarized in the review of Funes-Rodríguez et al. (2007). The
24 nutrient cycle, however, received very little attention. Although the Bahía-Magdalena is the most
25 well known system in the western Californian region, the inter- and intra-annual patterns of
26 nutrient dynamics and, consequently chlorophyll-*a* concentrations, still need to be examined in
27 depth. The research carried out, as little as it is, points to the local importance of coastal
28 upwelling (Álvarez-Borrego et al., 1975) and tidal currents (Acosta-Ruiz and Lara-Lara, 1978;
29 Guerrero-Godínez et al., 1988) in the fertilization of the lagoon. On a large scale, the seasonally
30 high biological production in the western lagoons of the Baja-California Peninsula might be
31 connected with the conditions in the southern boundary of the California Current System (Durazo
32 and Baumgartner, 2002; Durazo et al., 2005).

33 Therefore, in relation to nutrient input and phytoplankton activity (from chlorophyll levels), in
34 the coastal lagoon of Bahía-Magdalena it is hypothesized that, as result of a prevailing marine
35 influence, the fertilization process inside this lagoon is mainly due to coastal upwelling. In this
36 way, the objectives are as follows: (i) to identify and characterize the main intra-annual periods
37 highlighting the influence of the water masses that yearly are present in Bahia-Magdalena, in
38 particular, Sub-Arctic Water, Equatorial Subsurface Water and the mixing of both of them, the
39 Transitional Water; and (ii) to describe the inter-annual changes in the lagoon and to explore their
40 relationship with the California Current System. These objectives are based on forty-three
41 sampling cruises with a bimonthly frequency and 8-day composite satellite information for
42 Surface Sea Temperature and chlorophyll-*a*. Data were used to analyze the seasonal and inter-
43 annual variations for a period of seven years: from 2005 to 2011.

44 2. - MATERIAL AND METHODS

45 2.1. - Study area

46 The Bahía-Magdalena is a subtropical lagoon located on the southwestern coast of the
47 peninsula of Baja-California (Figure 1). Following the classification system for Mexican lagoons
48 (Lankford, 1977), Bahía-Magdalena has a tectonic structural origin and is a choked short inlet type
49 of coastal lagoon (Perillo *et al.*, 1999). The lagoon area covers 565 km² with a total water volume
50 (low-high tide) of 6.8-8.1 km³ (Sánchez-Montante *et al.*, 2007). The lagoon is separated from the
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1 Pacific Ocean by Margarita and Magdalena islands and sand bars that are protected from ocean
2 swells. The inner zone occupies half of the lagoon surface and is characterized by shallow
3 channels (<10 m in depth) surrounded by extensive mangrove areas. The deeper outer zone is
4 connected to the ocean through a mouth 5.6 km wide and 38 m in depth. The sediment of the
5 lagoon is relatively homogeneous with fine and very fine sands, except in the mangrove swamp
6 area where sludge is abundant (Sanchez *et al.*, 2010).

7 The offshore seawaters in Western Baja-California are under the influence of the southern
8 boundary of the California Current; NW winds prevail during most of the year and frequent and
9 intense upwelling events occur from April to June (Zaitsev *et al.*, 2003; Cervantes-Duarte *et al.*,
10 2010). In Bahía-Magdalena the weather is semi-arid. Air temperature ranges from 14° C in January
11 to 32° C in August-September (Sánchez *et al.*, 2010). The average annual precipitation varies
12 between 48 and 153 mm·yr⁻¹, collected mainly during summer (Sánchez *et al.*, 2010). The lagoon
13 does not receive river inputs and the continental freshwater sources are temporary streams. The
14 tidal regime is semidiurnal and its range is microtidal: 0.4-2.3 m (Obeso-Nieblas *et al.*, 1999). The
15 phytoplankton consists mainly of diatoms and dinoflagellates (Garate-Lizarraga *et al.*, 2007).

16 The population around the lagoon numbers approximately 10,000 inhabitants concentrated
17 in the towns of Puerto-San-Carlos and Puerto-Adolfo-López-Mateos, whose main economic
18 activity is artisanal fishery and the processing of tuna and sardine. The first of the two ports,
19 Puerto-San-Carlos is also used to embark phosphorite, extracted from ores of neighboring inland
20 areas.
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25 **2.2. - Coastal cruises**

26 Forty-three one-day sampling cruises were carried out in the lagoon of Bahía-Magdalena
27 during the period from 2005 to 2011 with a bimonthly frequency. The water column samples
28 were taken aboard CICIMAR-XV and CICIMAR-XXX research boats, during ebb tide conditions, in
29 fourteen stations in Bahía-Magdalena lagoon (Fig.1). Four of the stations were located in the
30 outer or oceanic zone (St. A-D; >10 m depth) and the remaining ten are shallows (≤10 m depth)
31 and correspond to the inner zone (St. 0-9) which is near to the littoral channels and mangroves
32 where the freshwater inputs should occur. Vertical profiles of temperature and salinity were
33 obtained at each station using a CTD Sea-Bird 19-Plus. Moreover, water samples from the surface
34 and bottom were collected, but only surface samples were taken in the shallow stations (St.4-7),
35 using 5-L General Oceanic Niskin bottles. Subsamples for the determination of nutrient salts and
36 chlorophyll-*a* were sampled from the bottles and refrigerated at 4° C to be processed in the port
37 laboratory during the same day.
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40 Air temperature in the lagoon was measured at the coastal meteorological station of San-
41 Carlos (Fig.1). Data were provided by the Mexican “Comisión Nacional del Agua”.
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44 **2.3. - Sampling treatment and analyses**

45 Immediately after arrival at the port water samples were filtered using a Millipore system
46 with fiberglass Whatman GFF filters of 25 mm in diameter. The content of the filter was used to
47 extract the chlorophyll according to the procedure of Venrick and Hayward (1984) and next to
48 quantify the chlorophyll concentration according to the Jeffrey and Humphrey (1975) method,
49 using a Spectronic Genesys-2 spectrophotometer. One aliquot of the filtered water was used to
50 determine the concentrations of ammonium, which were analyzed within 6 hours of collection.
51 Another part was stored in a freezer at -50° C for the subsequent analysis of nitrite, nitrate and
52 phosphate. These nutrient salts were determined with the standard spectrophotometry method
53 according to Strickland and Parsons (1972) using a Spectronic Genesys-2 device. The precision
54 from ten replicate analyses was ±0.1 mg·m⁻³ for chlorophyll, ±0.1 μM for nitrate and ammonium,
55 ±0.01 μM for nitrite and ±0.03 μM for phosphate.
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58 The spatio-temporal division of lagoon in two zones and two seasons was tacked by water
59 termohaline properties and biochemical characteristics one way ANOVA test analysis of principal
60 components (PCA) applied to the seven years period.
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2.4. - Satellite and upwelling index information

Eight-day composite data for Sea Surface Temperature (SST) and chlorophyll *a* were used to analyze seasonal and inter-annual variation during the 2005-2011 period. Data were collected in the outer zone of the lagoon from the satellite MODIS-AQUA, Level-3 with 4x4 km of spatial resolution available from ocean color home page: <http://www.oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi/13>. *In situ* data of SST and chlorophyll-*a* from the deepest stations in the outer zone of the lagoon (St. A-D) were averaged to be compared with the satellite data.

The periods of relaxation and intensification of the upwelling events were defined from the coastal upwelling index (UI) averaged every 8 days based on the data obtained daily from the Pacific Fisheries Environmental Laboratory database (http://www.pfeg.noaa.gov/pfel/about_pfel.html).

The inter-annual variability of cold and warmer events was described on the basis of the Multivariate ENSO Index (MEI) and SST anomaly for the 2005 to 2011 period.

3. – RESULTS

3.1. – Hydrographical conditions: thermohaline variables

The sea surface temperature data in the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon come from *in situ* measurements (IST) recorded during sampling cruises and from satellite measured values (SST). The results are shown in Figure 2 where the IST averaged for the four stations of the outer lagoon zone is compared with the SST grid of this outer zone on the same day of the cruise. Temperature (°C) from satellite and *in situ* are used both without distinction due to the correlation between their data was significant:

$$SST = 3.01 + 0.92 \cdot IST \quad (r = 0.94; n=43; p<0.05) \quad (1)$$

The temperature range applied to this equation was 16-28° C and close to these limits. As observed in Fig.3, satellite estimations tend to be underestimated (overestimated) when the *in-situ* temperature is low (high). Hence, during the period exhibiting the lowest annual temperature (winter-spring), the *in-situ* values are sometimes lower than the estimates recorded by satellite, while in the other period (summer-autumn) the opposite occurs (Figure 3).

Intra-annually the temperature in the lagoon of Bahia-Magdalena, according to both IST and SST, presented a markedly seasonal pattern with peaks from August to October and minima between March and May. There were no significant changes observed between surface and bottom temperatures ($p<0.05$; Table 1) in the lagoon and in the water column, the stations nearest to the mouth were the coldest during the first half of year (Table 1). Of the two lagoon zones, the outer deeper oceanic zone had lower temperature readings throughout the year. than the inner zone, which is mainly littoral and shallow, This difference, however, was not significant during the second half of the year ($p<0.05$; Table 1).

The water temperature in the upwelling areas is usually conditioned by the wind regime which moves the surface coastal waters seaward. This is quantified by the Upwelling Index (UI), which expresses the volume of water displaced by km of coastline during a given period of time. In the coastal area of the peninsula of Baja California adjacent to the lagoon of Bahía-Magdalena, the inter-annual variation of UI generally exhibits positive values (Fig.3), i.e. it is always favourable, to greater or lesser extent, to the upwelling year-round. Intra-annually upwelling conditions tend to present two peaks; one from March to May ($2000 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$; Fig.2) and another from September to November ($1300 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$; Fig.2). The maximum UI during the seven-year period covered was reached in March, April and May (particularly in the years 2006, 2010 and 2011), while some values of UI, averaged over eight-days, that were close to zero or negative, occurred in January-February and July-August.

Inter-annually, the temperature in the outer zone of the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon showed significant differences ($p<0.05$) between the first and the second half of the year. In terms of extreme temperatures during the January-June interval of the 2005-2011 period, 2005 was the

1 warmest year and 2008 the coldest, while during the July-December interval, the year 2008 was
2 the warmest and 2010 the coldest (Fig.3). This annual pattern during the two seasons runs
3 parallel to the oscillation of the air temperature (AT) in the littoral area of the lagoon (Fig.2). The
4 monthly average maximum of AT was recorded in August (34.3° C) and the minimum was found in
5 January (26.5° C) while the highest SST corresponded to the months of August-October (23.4-
6 27.2° C) and the lowest from March to May (16.8-20.4° C; Fig.2). If the inter-annual temperature
7 fluctuations for the period 2005 to 2011 (Fig.3) are expressed as monthly SST anomalies, the
8 alternation of warm and cold periods is emphasized. Hence, during the first half of 2005 the
9 average anomalies were positive or warm (+0.5° C) but during the second half of 2005 and the
10 first half of 2006, they were negative or cold (-1.0° C). A similar warm-cold pattern was observed
11 during the second half of 2006 and the first half of 2007 (+1.5° C) and the second half of 2007 and
12 the first half of 2008 (-1.2° C). Later there were two extended periods of time; one was warm
13 (+1.5° C) from the second half of 2008 to the first half of 2010 and the other, cold (-2.1° C) from
14 the second half of 2010 to the first half of 2011.

15 While the temperature pattern is clear, salinity presented a complex temporal distribution
16 with a mean value of 34.3±0.3 (Fig.3). In temporal terms, the highest salinity was observed in the
17 year 2011 and the lowest in 2005 (34.7 and 34.1, respectively; Fig.3). Spatially, the outer lagoon
18 zone showed a less variable mean salinity (34.2±0.2) in the first, rather than the second half of the
19 year (34.4±0.4; Table 1). On the contrary, salinity variations in the inner zone were more obvious,
20 reaching 35.0±0.7 in the first half and 35.1±0.8 in the second half of the year. In the water column
21 of the lagoon, salinity did not exhibit any significant differences between the surface and the
22 bottom (p<0.05; Table 1). However, salinities in the shallow inner area were significantly higher
23 than in the mouth during both semesters (p<0.05; Table 1).

24 Temperature and salinity values together make it possible to identify the water bodies that
25 are present in the Bahia-Magdalena lagoon during the seven-year study period. The influence of
26 upwelled seawater that reaches the lagoon must be higher near the bottom at the mouth. Thus
27 the salinity and temperature data in the four stations of the outer lagoon zone are shown in a TS
28 diagram (Figure 4). The data are clustered into three groups according to their own water mass
29 characteristics: Sub-Arctic Water (SAW), Subtropical Surface Water (StSW), Equatorial Subsurface
30 Water (ESsW), and Transitional Water (TrW) from SAW and StSW mixing, following the water
31 mass classification of Durazo and Baumgartner (2002) for the Pacific Oceanic Region of western
32 Baja California.

33 During the first yearly period until June, T-S values are largely associated with TrW while in
34 the second yearly period until December they belong to StSW in the inner and outer lagoon zones
35 both (Fig.4). However, in the outer zone exceptions were observed for some months between the
36 water masses associated with semi-annual seasons, mainly due to colder water conditions. During
37 the first semester, in April 2006 and June 2006-07-08 the seawater values of temperature and
38 salinity in the outer lagoon zone corresponded to ESsW instead of TrW. Similarly, during the
39 second semester the seawater in August 2007 and December 2007 and 2010 shifted from StSW to
40 TrW. In the inner zone of lagoon the salinity increases up to 38, mainly during summer.

41 **3.2. – Biogeochemical conditions: nutrients and chlorophyll-a distribution**

42 Concentrations of nutrient salts in Bahia-Magdalena waters did not exceed values of 16, 1,
43 19 and 3 µM for nitrate, nitrite, ammonium and phosphate, respectively. Although silicate cannot
44 be determined in the 2005-2011 period corresponding to the present study, a previous analysis
45 (2001-03; Cervantes-Duarte, pers. comm.) indicated that its concentration did not exceed 18 µM.

46 Intra-annually, the mean concentrations of nitrate and phosphate in the water lagoon were
47 higher during the first half of the year (Table 1). There is a significant seasonal (i.e. six-monthly)
48 difference (Table 1) for the two nutrients between the inner and outer zones of lagoon. Figure 5
49 shows a good seasonal correlation for each semester of the seven aforementioned years between
50 both nutrients (µM) in the outer lagoon zone:

$$51 \text{ First semester: } [\text{nitrate}] = 8.44 [\text{phosphate}] - 3.0 \quad (r = 0.95; n=7) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Second semester: } [\text{nitrate}] = 1.82 [\text{phosphate}] - 0.2 \quad (r=0.84; n=7) \quad (3)$$

During the first half-yearly season, the availability of nitrate and phosphate is higher than in the second season. Intra-annually, the higher influence of upwelling during the first semester was in parallel to nutrient increase (Fig.3). Moreover, there was also observed inter-annually variations of nutrients (Fig.3), i.e. in 2006 (5.8 and 1.0 μM of nitrate and phosphate, respectively), 2007 (3.9 and 0.85 μM), 2010 (2.7 and 0.64 μM) and 2011 (2.5 and 0.68 μM).

The mean concentration of ammonium was higher during the first half of the year, but, unlike nitrate and phosphate, ammonium does not exhibit any significant differences between the external and internal areas of the lagoon or between the surface and bottom (Table 1) during this season. This spatial homogeneity does not continue on a temporal basis since there are statistically significant differences between the first and second half of the year (Table 1), associated with a greater concentration of ammonium near the littoral zone during the second season.

In the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon chlorophyll concentrations reached 17 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and the dissolved oxygen saturation percentage varied between 70-130%, which indicates a high biological activity associated with the availability of nutrient salts reported earlier. The mean concentrations of chlorophyll-*a* in the stations close to the mouth of the lagoon, i.e. its outer zone, were comparatively higher during the first versus the second half of the year (2.8 and 1.7 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, respectively; Table 1). Chlorophyll-*a* ranges did not show any significant differences ($p<0.05$) between the surface and bottom areas of the whole lagoon, but in both semesters, the concentration of Chlorophyll-*a* increased in the inner zone close to the shallow littoral zone, (2.2-3.5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$; Table 1). The annual variation in chlorophyll showed a six-monthly pattern with its highest concentrations found at the end of the first season and the lowest at the end of the second season (Fig.2).

The chlorophyll-*a* analysis from *in situ* and satellite values, was significant. However, the values estimated from satellite measurements had a greater dynamic range with respect to the measurement *in situ* (Fig.2). The correlation between both estimates was:

$$\text{Chlorophyll-a (mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\text{): } [\text{satellite}] = 1.76 [\textit{in situ}] - 0.20 \quad (r=0.74; n=42; p<0.05) \quad (4)$$

The overestimation of chlorophyll-*a* concentrations from satellite measurements was already pointed out in the region of California Current by Kahru and Mitchell (2001). These authors indicated that the chlorophyll-*a* correlation between satellite and *in situ* data is higher offshore than near the coast. It may be associated with the inshore increase of colouring dissolved organic matter from sources different to phytoplankton.

Inter-annually, both satellite and *in situ* trends were similar in the lagoon. The period from 2005 to 2011 showed increases in the average concentrations of chlorophyll in 2008 (3.0 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$; Fig.3) and 2010 (2.7 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), while 2009 (1.8 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), 2006 and 2011 (2.0 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) were less productive years. This inter-annual chlorophyll-*a* pattern correlates with the temperature (Fig.5) of the outer lagoon zone. There, the chlorophyll-*a* concentration increases when the water temperature decreases. This occurs during the two seasons of the year in the lagoon, although during the second season, the temperature was higher and the levels of chlorophyll-*a* lower. In both cases there was a good correlation between chlorophyll-*a* concentration (Chl-*a* in $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the outer lagoon zone:

$$\text{First semester: } [\text{Chl-a}] = 13.4 - 0.62\cdot T \quad (r=0.93; n=6) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Second semester: } [\text{Chl-a}] = 9.2 - 0.32\cdot T \quad (r=0.83; n=6) \quad (6)$$

3.3. – Spatio-temporal zoning

The main oceanographic patterns in the subtropical lagoon of Bahía-Magdalena during the 2005-2011 period can be studied on the basis of the variables measured seasonally and averaged every year, i.e. the first (February-July) and second (August-January) semester, in each lagoon zone, i.e. inner and outer areas. Therefore, a factorial analysis may explain the response variables during those seven years, as a function of explanatory thermohaline and biogeochemical variables. This resulted in the extraction of two factors that explain 64% of the variance in the PCA

1 of Figure 6. Factor 1 (37% of the contribution to the total variance) displayed high positive scores
2 for nutrient salts (nitrate, ammonium and phosphate), and negative scores for temperature and
3 oxygen saturation. Factor 2 (27% of the contribution to the total variance) loaded positively in
4 salinity and chlorophyll-*a*, and negatively in the depth of the Secchi disk. It provided an annual
5 season-zone division to the lagoon following the four quadrants of PCA regardless of the year. The
6 first quadrant comprises the inner zone and the first season; the second, the outer zone and first
7 season; the third, the outer zone and second season; and the fourth, the inner zone and second
8 season (Fig.6).
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10 11 **4. - DISCUSSION**

12 Thermohaline and biogeochemical variables were able to identify an inner zone that is
13 associated with depths lower than 20 m in the subtropical lagoon of Bahía-Magdalena. This
14 shallow zone occupies approximately 80% of the lagoon area and it is characterized by a
15 homogeneous vertical distribution of salinity and temperature. Salinity increased near the littoral,
16 where there are intertidal channels, and during summer. According to the explanation given by
17 Zaitsev et al. (2010) it has to do with the main physical processes affecting the thermohaline
18 structure, such as tidal transport and surface heat in Bahia-Magdalena. Moreover, this vertical
19 homogeneity may be extended to the nutrients and chlorophyll in the water column of the
20 shallow lagoon zone. This inner pattern is due to the absence of freshwater contributions towards
21 the lagoon, which is located in a semi-arid climate region. This fact makes a key difference
22 between Bahia-Magdalena and other subtropical lagoons where the fluvial contributions fertilize
23 the inner areas and give rise to a vertical stratification in salinity and nutrients (Caffrey et al.,
24 2007; Murrell et al., 2007; Philips et al., 2012). So, in the subtropical lagoons with estuarine zones
25 the nutrient inputs are mainly connected with the rainfall season (Eyre 2000; Lehrter 2008; Abreu
26 et al., 2010) and chlorophyll concentration increased up to four times the observed during the dry
27 season (Philips et al., 2012). On a local level in Bahia-Magdalena, the presence of a mangle forest
28 in the littoral zone (Acosta Velázquez and Ruiz-Luna, 2007) and the phosphorite ores from
29 neighboring areas that are loaded at San-Carlos port increased the ammonium and phosphate
30 concentrations in the shore waters.
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32 Consequently, in keeping with the typology of Abreu et al. (2010), Bahia-Magdalena can be
33 classified among the coastal lagoons which have a prevailing marine influence, such as was
34 emphasized by the salinities higher than 35 in the inner lagoon zone, showing the very scarce
35 continental freshwater inputs during all the year (Fig.4). It is in the outer zone of the lagoon
36 where the influence of the sea can be clearly identified. This outer zone is characterized by its
37 situation close to the sea-mouth of the lagoon and depths greater than 20 m. Temperature-
38 salinity diagrams show the influence of upwelling events within the lagoon (Fig.4). The incoming
39 seawater corresponds to the typical water mass classification off the western coast of Baja
40 California (Durazo and Baumgartner 2002). Therefore, the three main groups of the Pacific
41 Oceanic Region of western Baja California (Durazo and Baumgartner, 2002) have been observed in
42 the lagoon: TrW in the California Current (CCW), and to a lesser extent ESsW, prevailing during
43 the February-July season, while StSW was mainly associated with the August-January season
44 (Fig.4). The boundary between the seawater transported by CCW, i.e. TrW and SAW, and the
45 saltier and warmer StSW, i.e. the temperate-tropical transition (Lluch-Belda et al., 2003), moves
46 northward during late summer and fall. Then, tropical and subtropical waters are observed
47 farther to the north (Durazo, 2009). In this annual period, the coastal lagoon of Bahía-Magdalena
48 was under the domain of StSW while the influence of the CCW coincided in time with the
49 intensification of the California Current (Schwartzlose and Reid 1972), associated with the coastal
50 upwelling induced by the prevailing north-westerly wind in the period from March to June.
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52 Bahía-Magdalena belongs to the type of marine-domain coastal lagoon, but unlike the most
53 of these subtropical types, Bahia-Magdalena is different because it is situated in a perennial
54 upwelling region. However, upwelling is not a temporally continuous or spatially uniform process;
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1 rather it displays periods of more favourable conditions. Along the entire coast of the peninsula of
2 California, the upwelling intensity changes in accordance with local wind conditions and bottom
3 topography (Zaitsev et al., 2003). There is an intensification of the spring upwelling activity
4 towards the middle latitudes. Average UI magnitudes for the Magdalena Bay latitude (24° N) were
5 three times lower than for the Ensenada location (31° N) for the period from April through June.
6 Moreover, the duration of upwelling events is also shorter in Bahía-Magdalena, 4-5 days (Zaitsev
7 et al., 2003; Durazo et al., 2010) than in the north-eastern zone, i.e. two weeks at Point
8 Conception (34.5°N; Wilkerson et al., 2006). There is a very little scientific knowledge on
9 subtropical coastal-upwelling lagoons although at 30° N on the Californian Peninsula there is
10 another similar coastal system, the Bahía-de-San-Quintín (42 km² and 20 m in depth at its mouth).
11 In this subtropical lagoon influenced by the California Current System, upwelling events and tides
12 are the main causes of variability in the lagoon's hydrographical properties (Millan-Nuñez et al.,
13 1982; Alvarez-Borrego, 2004).
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15 The temporal pattern in the Bahia-Magdalena lagoon shows the nutrient dependence of
16 upwelling events (Fig.3). So, among the coastal lagoons presenting a prevailing maritime influence
17 (Abreu et al., 2010), this coastal system corresponds to an unusual type of subtropical coastal
18 lagoon where its water is under fertilization by upwelling phenomena. This Bahia-Magdalena
19 pattern was also observed in temperate ria systems (Evans and Prego, 2003) with seasonal
20 upwelling (Fraga, 1981; Prego and Bao, 1997). During spring-summer in the Western and Middle
21 Galician Rias of the Iberian Peninsula the fluvial contributions are very low; hence nutrient input
22 as result of upwelling events is the main reason for the fertilization of the ria (Prego, 2002; Varela
23 et al., 2008). In both systems, the subsurface nutrient-rich water upwells: The Eastern North
24 Atlantic Central water mass in the case of the rias (up to 12 µM of nitrate; Prego et al., 1999) and
25 the Sub-Arctic water mass in the California Current in the case of Bahia-Magdalena, which is
26 below 100 m depth and upwells to the surface (Zaitsev *et al.*, 2003; Durazo 2009; Durazo *et al.*,
27 2010). Under upwelling conditions in the western shelf of the Baja-California region, Pennington
28 and Chávez (2000) indicated nitrate concentrations of 7-20 µM in the Bay of Monterey, from May
29 to June and Ribas-Ribas et al. (2011) measured up to 12 µM of nitrate in the Bay of San-Quintín.
30 Moreover, during the period of high upwelling intensity (March-June) nitrate concentrations
31 increased up to 15 µM in the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon. The phytoplankton pattern in this lagoon
32 (Gárate-Lizarraga et al., 2007) and the chlorophyll-*a* concentrations (Fig.2), both of which
33 increased to reach maximum values in June, allow for a high exploitation of marine resources
34 (fishes, mollusks and crustaceans; Funes-Rodríguez et al., 2007) in the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon. It
35 is mainly supported by nutrient inputs from upwelling in the February-July period.
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41 The spatial (inner and outer areas) and temporal (February-July and August-January
42 semesters) duality of the subtropical lagoon of Bahía-Magdalena during the 2005-2011 period is
43 repeated year to year. The PCA grouping (Fig.6) shows how the intra-annual pattern is recurrent
44 according to the pattern described in the previous section. The oceanographic parameters in the
45 outer lagoon zone during the 2005-2011 period (M points in the Fig.6) varied between cold and
46 warm half-yearly periods in association with the California Current water and Subtropical Surface
47 Water alternation off the Baja-California region (Goericke *et al.*, 2007; Bjorkstedt *et al.*, 2010).
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49 In this trend some minor differences can be noticed. During the first semester in the outer
50 lagoon zone, 2006 and 2007 are the furthest on the X-axis of Fig.6, which implies that they are the
51 coldest (17.2, and 17.9° C, respectively) and most nutrient abundant years (9.8 and 6.1 µM-NO₃,
52 respectively) of the seven years period. The meteorological conditions of these two years
53 presented an increase in the upwelling tailwinds of the southern California Current region
54 (Peterson et al., 2006; Goericke et al., 2007). On the contrary, upwelling intensities were low the
55 years 2010 and 2011 and there were low differences between chlorophyll-*a* concentrations
56 between their first and second semester seasons (Fig.3 and equations 5 and 6). Both semesters
57 were close together in the inner lagoon zone (Fig.6), which indicates that no significant
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1 differences occurred throughout these years. Moreover, in 2010-11 the points corresponding to
2 the outer zone and the first semester were closest to the X-origin (Fig.6), i.e. a year with low
3 upwelling intensities. During 2005 and 2010 unusually cold waters were recorded in the south
4 California region, resulting from intense upwelling (Peterson et al., 2006), but there was no
5 information on the Bahía-Magdalena coast. However, in spring 2010, warm conditions were
6 observed together with an increase in gelatinous zooplankton (Bjorkstedt et al., 2010). Lastly,
7 2009 was an unusual year with regard to the position of the outer points close to the end of the
8 negative ordinate axis (Fig.6); 2009 was an atypical year. During 2009, the negative Pacific Decadal
9 Oscillation index of 2007-08 returned to normal (McClatchie et al., 2009).

10 In the world, different temporal trends were observed as result of the climate forcing on the
11 upwelling variability. So, in the California Current region (32-40°N) an increase in the seasonal
12 upwelling was pointed out by Schwing and Mendelsohn (1998), similarly to those reported for
13 the coastal upwelling areas off North-West Africa and Peru (Bakun 2001; Narayan et al. 2010). The
14 time series of seven years (2005-2011) obtained in the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon show an
15 ambiguous trend, in accordance with the 24-27°N result from the latitudinal model developed by
16 Bakun (1990). However, Kahru et al. (2012) detected a decrease in the chlorophyll concentration
17 in the Southern Baja-California zone; they attributed it to a reduction in the upwelling intensity. It
18 can be speculate that the upwelling decrease in the Bahía-Magdalena lagoon should modify the
19 chlorophyll levels during the boundary months between the two seasons; so, the warm pattern
20 will prevail over the cold and the lagoon could become biologically less productive. Longer time
21 series in Bahía-Magdalena lagoon are necessities for researching the impact of climate on
22 oceanographic changes.
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25 **Figure Captions**

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27 Figure 1. Location, bathymetry and sampling stations in the subtropical coastal lagoon of Bahía-
28 Magdalena. Letters A-D correspond to the four stations located in the outer lagoon
29 zone while the ten stations numbered 0-9 are within the inner lagoon zone.
- 30 Figure 2. Monthly average values during the period 2005-2011: (A) upwelling index (UI); (B) air
31 temperature and sea surface temperature; and (C) surface chlorophyll-*a*. The grey
32 circles correspond to satellite records and the triangles to *in situ* measurements.
33 Dashed lines and bars represent one standard deviation of the seven year period.
- 34 Figure 3. Seven year record of the temporary variation of the surface values of temperature,
35 chlorophyll-*a*, salinity, nitrate, phosphate and upwelling index (UI) in the outer zone
36 of Bahía-Magdalena lagoon. The squares show the monthly average of the four outer
37 stations, and the line corresponds to satellite and 8-day averaged UI data.
- 38 Figure 4. Temperature-Salinity diagram showing the lagoon bottom data of the outer (Stations A-
39 D) and the inner (Stations 0-9) zone. Shaded and empty symbols correspond to the
40 first and second semester of the year, respectively. TSW is the acronym for Tropical
41 Surface Water; StSW, Subtropical Surface Water; TrW, Transitional Water; SAW,
42 Subarctic Water; and ESsW, Equatorial Subsurface Water (Durazo and Baumgartner,
43 2002).
- 44 Figure 5. Relationships of (A) chlorophyll-*a* vs temperature and (B) nitrate vs phosphate. Surface *in*
45 *situ* data of the outer lagoon zone were semester averaged for each year of the 2005-
46 2011 period; empty and shaded symbols correspond to the first and second semester,
47 respectively.
- 48 Figure 6. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) applied to the *in situ* surface data of salinity,
49 temperature, nitrate, phosphate chlorophyll-*a* and depth of the Secchi disk. They
50 were temporary-spatially averaged by lagoon zone and semester of the period 2005-
51 2011. Letter M and L, correspond to the outer and inner lagoon zones, respectively;
52 the following number represents the first (1) or second (2) semesters of the year and
53 the number after the media bar shows the last two digits of the years 2005-2011.
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Table I. Mean values and standard deviation. The significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between zones in each layer and season (1st and 2nd semesters) were calculated applying the Kruskal-Wallis One Way Analysis of Variance on ranks. Results are showed according to the upper-index "a, b, c, d".

Layer	Zone-semester	Temperature (°C)	Salinity	Nitrate (μM)	Ammonium (μM)	Phosphate (μM)	Oxygen (% saturation)	Chlorophyll- <i>a</i> ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
Surface	^a Outer-1	18.0±1.9 ^{bcd}	34.3±0.3 ^{cd}	5.0±5.2 ^{bcd}	3.7±3.0 ^{bd}	0.94±0.52 ^{bd}	100±16	2.7±1.9 ^b
	^b Outer-2	23.2±2.5 ^{ac}	34.4±0.4 ^{cd}	0.9±1.0 ^a	1.4±2.0 ^{ac}	0.54±0.22 ^{acd}	98±15	1.7±1.4 ^{acd}
	^c Inner-1	19.8±1.8 ^{abd}	35.0±0.7 ^{ab}	2.4±3.6 ^a	3.3±2.8 ^{bd}	0.84±0.38 ^{abc}	96±21	2.8±2.5 ^b
	^d Inner-2	24.0±2.7 ^{ac}	35.1±0.8 ^{ab}	1.1±1.7 ^a	1.4±2.4 ^{ac}	0.70±0.25 ^{ab}	93±15	3.1±2.4 ^b
Bottom	^a Outer-1	15.3±1.9 ^{bcd}	34.4±0.2 ^{cd}	12.2±5.2 ^{bcd}	2.2±1.2	2.08±0.71 ^{bd}	67±16 ^c	2.7±2.1 ^b
	^b Outer-2	19.6±3.2 ^{ad}	34.4±0.3 ^{cd}	6.4±6.2 ^a	2.5±2.1	0.92±0.42 ^a	81±14 ^c	0.9±0.4 ^{ad}
	^c Inner-1	19.2±2.0 ^{ad}	35.3±0.8 ^{ab}	6.4±5.8 ^a	3.7±2.5	1.46±0.82 ^d	99±13 ^{abd}	3.5±2.0 ^d
	^d Inner-2	22.7±2.9 ^{acd}	35.5±1.1 ^{ab}	2.8±3.2 ^a	2.5±2.6	0.94±0.34 ^{ac}	79±11 ^c	2.2±1.9 ^{bc}

Figure(s)

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Fig.4

Figure 5

Figure 7